

TYPES OF LAND USE

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Abstract. *The relevance of land use intensifies in the context of economic reforms, the restructuring of land relations, and the incorporation of new economic, social, and ecological factors into the mechanism of rational and effective land use. Rational and effective land use is manifested through its multifaceted role in society, encompassing production, market dynamics, social welfare, recreational health improvement, and environmental protection. Thus, land possesses a socio-economic character.*

Keywords: *economic reforms, transport, communications, defense, nature protection, health improvement, recreation.*

Currently, effective land use is contingent upon a multifunctional and targeted approach. As of January 1, 2024, the total land area within the administrative boundaries of the Republic of Uzbekistan amounts to 44,892.4 thousand hectares. Based on their intended use, land resources are classified into eight categories.

- agricultural lands;
- land of settlements;
- land intended for industry, transport, communications, defense and other purposes,
- land intended for nature protection, health improvement, recreation,
- land of historical and cultural significance;
- land of forest fund;
- land of water fund;
- reserve lands

Information on the categories of the land fund of the Republic of Uzbekistan is presented in Table 1. The division of the land fund of the republic according to its economic objectives depends on the difference in the functions performed by the lands provided for use for certain purposes.

The development of a market economy has given land use a market and fiscal character. This situation has strengthened the role of land as an important object of socio-economic relations and relations in society. In turn, with the development of society, the requirements for the multi-purpose nature of land use become more complex, the forms and nature of land use change, this situation determines its dialectical nature, characterizes it as a constantly developing process. The main aspects of land use are: social, economic, recreational and ecological.

The agrarian method is associated with the use of the soil layer of the earth for growing agricultural crops. Here, the land is embodied as the main means of production. In turn, it can be

divided into methods of land use by types of technologies for sowing agricultural crops, planting perennial trees and using zero pastures, irrigated agriculture and dry farming.

Information on the categories of the land fund of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Table 1

Land categories	as of January 1, 2024 (thousand hectares)	%
Agricultural lands;	26132,2	58,21
Land of settlements;	226,7	0,51
Lands intended for industry, transport, communications, defense and other purposes,	786,9	1,75
Lands for nature conservation, health, recreational purposes,	3223,3	7,18
Lands of historical and cultural significance;	15,0	0,03
Lands of the forest fund;	12092,5	26,94
Lands of the water fund;	827,3	1,84
Reserve lands	1588,5	3,54
Total lands	44892,4	100

The industrial-production method provides for the adaptation of land plots in width in order to accommodate industrial, transport, service and trade facilities during their existence and maintaining them in a stationary state. The result of land use in both directions is economic efficiency, including the receipt of paid services. Industrial and transport facilities are often considered as generators of modes, the normal operation of which requires the creation of a region.

To improve the effectiveness of health treatment, natural properties of the earth are used, such as therapeutic mud, mineralized water, and climatic features. The field of nature conservation is characterized by a natural way of using land with flora and fauna, based on environmental efficiency, without technogenic impact on it.

The assessment of land for various purposes is associated with the nature of their intended use and the types of efficiency obtained. One or another method of land assessment is selected depending on the purpose of land use and types of efficiency. Let us consider the types of land use efficiency from the point of view of various purposes.

Land use in agriculture and forestry is associated with the procurement and production of timber from agricultural crops, i.e. with economic efficiency and the corresponding income from land use. Land use in agriculture and forestry is associated with economic efficiency, as well as with environmental efficiency; both types of efficiency can be positive or negative. The presence of economic efficiency of land use allows the use of the income method in assessing land for this purpose.

Industrial lands are less active in the production process than agricultural lands. Although land exists in this place as a means of production, it is not as important as agriculture. Nevertheless, even in this case, there is economic efficiency of land use, the calculation of the relative income corresponding to the means of production - land, here is a rather complex and poorly studied problem.

This makes it difficult to assess productive lands in terms of income. The above rules regarding the efficiency of industrial land use are also valid for lands of trade and service facilities. Here, too, new economic efficiency arises, but here, too, the problem of calculating the relative income of the means of production on land is not fixed, as a result of which the application of the income method to land assessment is difficult.

The economic efficiency of land use, the market value of minerals on the domestic or foreign market, the costs of their extraction and land reclamation, in turn, depend on the depth of occurrence of minerals, as well as their relative sizes. If the value of minerals is an active factor in the efficiency of land use, then the costs of their development will be a secondary factor. In this case, it is also necessary to determine the relative amount of income corresponding to land as a means of production. This allows using the income method when assessing land for this purpose.

The use of transport land is also associated with obtaining economic benefits. For production purposes, as in all cases of land use, it is problematic to obtain profit from land as a means of production. Determining this indicator allows using the income method when assessing the target land plot in question.

From the point of view of market relations, the land market is a specific area of land use, where land plays the role of a commodity. Economic efficiency will appear in the implementation of market actions, income from the sale of a land plot, but the peculiarity of land valuation in this case is that the land market can be primary and secondary. In the first case, only normative valuation methods can be used, since there is no economic benefit from selling land when creating a primary market. Here, the problem of determining the normative value of land also arises, the amount of income from its future sale is unknown and has no justification from the market point of view, and it is almost impossible to apply the income method of valuation. In the second case, the land valuation is determined on the basis of sales of other land plots that took place in the last period. Therefore, in this case, it is impossible to use the income method of land valuation, other similar methods are needed.

The use of land in the social sphere is associated with the use of land for the construction of houses (single-family, multi-family), preschool institutions, schools, colleges and institutions, clinics and hospitals, libraries and other social facilities. However, the lack of study of the assessment of the social efficiency of land use makes it difficult to carry out a social assessment of land. Nature reserves, private parks, national parks and recreation areas - swimming areas, ship stations, forests, mountain slopes, tourist bases, etc. Because of this, it is very difficult to evaluate these lands. If it is of a recreational nature, then in such cases the use of these lands will have not only recreational, but also economic benefits. It should be said that the economic and social efficiency of land is always accompanied by environmental efficiency. The use of land in any area of activity of modern society gives at least two types of results, one of which is always environmental efficiency. This situation is explained by the fact that the land used by society as a land resource for various purposes is simultaneously the main element of the natural complex, and its use by society is reflected in the state of the environment. In particular, the use of land in agriculture is associated with a decrease in land productivity and a number of its characteristics, as well as the restoration of soil fertility and the improvement of meliorative conditions.

To assess multi-purpose lands, it is necessary to divide the studied array or land plot into sectors by the purpose of use and determine the efficiency of individual land use for each of them in accordance with its purpose, and then find the total efficiency of its multi-purpose use. Each

type of efficiency has its own natural indicators, and to calculate the total efficiency of all organizations, it is necessary to reduce them to a single indicator, that is, give them the form of a value. The ability to calculate the total efficiency of multi-purpose land plots allows for an income assessment of all land plots.

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